

Linear Voltage Regulator Stability Analysis through Phase Margin Measurement

Analisis Kestabilan Pengatur Voltan Linear Melalui Pengukuran Jidar Fasa

Muhammad Aidil Ibrahim, Mohd Hairi Mohd Zaman, Ahmad Asrul Ibrahim, Asraf Mohamed Moubark
Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

ABSTRACT

Most linear voltage regulators require an output capacitor with specific value of internal parasitic element called equivalent series resistance (ESR). This ESR range must be characterized to ensure the stability of the voltage regulator is guaranteed. Instability of the linear voltage regulator such as indicated by excessive overshoot and undershoot of output voltage give negative effect on the electronic devices. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the range of ESR through phase margin measurement. LTspice simulation software was used to simulate a voltage regulator circuit, that contains an adjustable ESR as well as load. This software was also used to assist in the process of detailing the value of ESR and determining the output voltage stability through phase margin measurements. To conclude, this research able to identify the ESR range that need to be used to produce stable output voltage.

ABSTRAK

Kebanyakan pengatur voltan linear memerlukan satu kapasitor keluaran dengan satu julat nilai elemen parasitik dalaman tertentu dipanggil rintangan sesiri setara (ESR). Rintangan sesiri setara ini mestilah dicirikan bagi memastikan kestabilan pengatur voltan dapat dijamin. Ketidakstabilan pengatur voltan linear seperti yang ditunjukkan oleh lajukan dan lajak bawah yang melampau dalam voltan keluaran memberi kesan buruk kepada peranti elektronik. Oleh yang demikian, kajian ini bertujuan untuk mengkaji julat ESR melalui pengukuran jidar fasa. Perisian simulasi LTspice telah digunakan untuk melaksanakan simulasi sebuah litar pengatur voltan linear, yang mengandungi satu rintangan sesiri setara beban boleh laras. Perisian ini juga digunakan untuk membantu proses perincian nilai ESR dan penentuan kestabilan voltan keluaran melalui pengukuran jidar fasa. Kesimpulannya, kajian ini dapat mengenalpasti julat ESR yang perlu digunakan bagi menghasilkan voltan keluaran yang stabil.

INTRODUCTION

Most circuits in electronic devices require a constant and stable DC supply without being affected by the changes of input voltage or load condition.(Chava and Silva-Martinez 2002) This stable output voltage is typically provided by the voltage regulator (VR). An output capacitor, with optimum internal parasitic element called equivalent series resistance (ESR), is connected to VR output terminal to ensure stability.(Day 2002). Even though ESR is important for compensation, its value increases due to temperature and aging factors, and may cause VR instability (Evolution, n.d.)Therefore, VR stability, in terms of ESR, through phase margin measurement is needed. To determine the stability from phase margin, we need to have phase margin from open loop feedback system.(Lai 2009)This is because the actual VR

model is difficult to be accurately determined due to manufacturing process variation factor.

Voltage regulators are widely used in many areas such as equipment or devices in space and military, automotive, industrial and so on.(T S 2012). There are two main types of voltage regulators i.e. linear type voltage regulator and switching type voltage regulator. Usually, linear voltage regulators have wider bandwidth of control loop and faster response compare to switching type of voltage regulator.(Zhang 2013)

However, this study focuses more on linear voltage regulators. Voltage regulators can also be classified into two types i.e. voltage regulator with fixed output voltage and voltage regulator with adjustable output voltage.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1(a) shows the VR simulation circuit used in this study. It consists of a MOSFET as its pass element. To test the stability of VR, the load current was abruptly changed by a signal generator, V4. All components in the circuit have been calculated to ensure VR able to compensate any disturbance such

as abrupt load current change. Meanwhile, Figure 1(b) indicates the test circuit to obtain the open-loop frequency response of VR.

Figure 1 Voltage regulator simulation circuit: (a) Load transient test circuit (b) Open-loop frequency response test circuit

To determine the values of R2, C1, and C2, following equation is utilized, where f_c is the cut-off frequency of the open-loop frequency response of VR:

$$f_c = \frac{0.24}{C_{out} \times R_c} \quad (1)$$

To find the phase boost that can compensate any disturbance occurred in the VR output, equation (2)

is used, which φm is the phase margin obtained from the open-loop frequency response:

$$boost = \varphi m - \arg T(f_c) - 90^\circ \quad (2)$$

For example, to provide a phase boost at a 12-kHz crossover frequency, a pole and zero are placed at:

$$f_p = \tan\left(\frac{boost}{2} + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) f_c \quad (3)$$

$$f_z = \tan\left(\frac{f_c}{\frac{boost}{2} + \frac{\pi}{4}}\right) f_c \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the value of R2 is,

$$R2 = \frac{R4f_pG}{f_p - f_z} \sqrt{\frac{\left(\frac{f_c}{f_p}\right)^2 + 1}{\left(\frac{f_z}{f_c}\right)^2 + 1}} \quad (5)$$

Meanwhile, the values of capacitance C1 and C2 are,

$$C1 = \frac{1}{2\pi R2 f_z} \quad (6)$$

$$C2 = \frac{C1}{2\pi f_p C1 R2 - 1} \quad (7)$$

Figure 2 shows the load transient response when the VR is unstable. It can be clearly seen that there are a number of oscillations in this time domain response. This condition was obtained when ESR is equals to 10 Ohm.

Figure 2 Output voltage of 10 Ohm ESR

Figure 3 Bode plot with phase margin indicated for 10 Ohm ESR

Figure 3 shows the results of an unstable phase margin which the phase is at 240° , where this measurement is obtained when making a straight

line from 0dB in Figure 3. The phase margin of Figure 3 is unstable because the phase margin is high at 60° , as computed using following equations,

$$\begin{aligned} PM &= 180^\circ - \Delta\phi \\ PM &= 180^\circ - 240^\circ \\ PM &= -60^\circ \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4 displays the load transient response when ESR is 500 mOhm. It can be seen that there is no oscillation occurred which indicates very good stability. Referring to Figure 5, the phase margin is 45° , which is the most stable phase margin. This value can be computed as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} PM &= 180^\circ - \Delta\phi \\ PM &= 180^\circ - 135^\circ \\ PM &= 45^\circ \end{aligned}$$

Based on the calculation, it shows that the most stable output voltage produced by VR is when using 500 mΩ ESR.

Figure 4 Output voltage of 500 mOhm ESR

Figure 5 Phase margin in open-loop frequency response for 500 mOhm ESR

Figure 6 shows the relationship between phase margin, ESR and current load. The most stable output voltage is when the phase margin in the range of 40° to 60° .

Figure 6 Relationship between phase margin, ESR and load current

Figure 7 Relationship between number of oscillation, ESR and load current

Figure 7 shows the relationship between number of oscillation, ESR and current load. In this study, if the number of oscillation is less than three, the VR is considered as stable. As the load current and ESR increase, the number of oscillation also increases. This indicates the VR becomes unstable as the ESR increases.

CONCLUSION

The impact of ESR variation to the VR output voltage stability can be determined using phase margin measurement. Stable VR output voltage has specific ESR range and its corresponding with phase margin for various loading conditions.

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